

Improved Findability of Energy Research Software by Introducing a Metadata-based Registry

Stephan Ferez, Astrid Nieße
Department of Computer Science
Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg

Agenda

- Motivation
- Vision
- Related Work
- Approach
- First Requirements for the Metadata Schema
- Summary and Outlook

Motivation: Software in Energy Research

- Components of energy systems
 - Visualization of lab data
 - Simulation of behavior
- Control strategies for energy (distribution) systems
 - Simulation of different components
 - Optimization of control strategies
- Grid planning
- Transition of the energy system
 - Optimization in a large scale

> Energy Research Software (ERS) is fundamental for Energy Research

Motivation: Challenges for Energy Research Software

- Increasing complexity
 - Provided code hardly findable
 - Software rarely reused
-
- Multiple frameworks with overlapping features
 - A lot of time spent to develop code which already exist somewhere
 - Code is often only use once
 - High development costs

➤ ERS needs to become more findable to be reused

Motivation: Findable Energy Research Software

- From the FAIR criteria [1,2]:
 - Findability can be improved through
 - good general metadata
 - registration of a software with metadata in a registry
 - Accessibility and Interoperability can be improved through
 - good metadata as context
 - Reuse can be simplified
 - metadata including conditions for reuse as license and how to cite

Metadata and a Metadata Registry can make Energy Research Software more Findable

Vision

Metadata-based Registry for Energy Research Software

General Requirements 1/2

- Useable for all types of energy research software
 - From long-term to short-term
- Application profile for energy research software
 - Reuses elements from existing metadata schemas
 - Improves FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
 - Follows best practice in metadata schema creation
 - Uses ontologies as value vocabularies
 - Compatible with existing metadata, e.g., PyPI

General Requirements 2/2

- Registry
 - Repository for metadata
 - Includes good search functionality
 - Supports all features of the application profile
 - Gives information on link-ability of software based on their metadata
- Metadata Generation Tool
 - Usable for all researchers in the energy domain without further knowledge
 - Automatically collects metadata from GitHub, GitLab, Google Scholar
 - Supports the use of value vocabularies (existing ontologies)

Related Work

Scope					
CodeMeta	General Research Software	✗	✓	✗	~
OntoSoft	Research Software in GeoScience	✗	✓	✓	~
Bio.Tools	Research Software in LifeScience	✗	~	✓	~
EngMeta	Research Data in Engineering	~	✓	~	✓
Open Energy Platform	Research Software in Energy Research	✓	~	✓	~

Open Energy Platform

Framework Factsheet: Mosaik

- Framework Factsheet
 - Not a formalized schema
 - Not based on existing schemas
 - Does not yet support the use of a value vocabulary
- Open Energy Ontology [10]
 - Domain Ontology for the energy domain
 - Can be used for annotating data & software

Overview

Last updated ?	2021-05-08
Open Source ?	✓
License ?	GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0

General Information

Mathematical Description

Openness

Model Building

References

Our Approach

Development of Domain Model

- Like proposed by Curado Malta and Baptista [4])
- The domain model
 - includes all relevant elements to describe ERS
 - is the foundation for a metadata schema

Development of Domain Model based on a Requirement Analysis

Interviews with Energy Researchers

Field of Expertise

Domain model based on interviews

Interesting Insights from the Interviews

- Most interviewees are interested in
 - the existing community of an ERS
 - the ways they can get support when using the tool
 - in quickly getting a good understanding of what the tool exactly does
 - in seeing compatible software and data

Summary and Outlook

– What is needed to set up a metadata-based registry which can improve the Findability of Energy Research Software?

– Approach

 – Domain Model based on a Requirement Analysis

 – Metadata Schema for ERS

 – Registry for ERS

– Metadata Generation Tool for ERS

Appendix: Literature

- [1] M. D. Wilkinson *et al.*, “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship,” *Sci Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18
- [2] A.-L. Lamprecht *et al.*, “Towards FAIR principles for research software,” *Data Science*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 37–59, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3233/DS-190026.
- [3] M. Booshehri *et al.*, “Introducing the Open Energy Ontology: Enhancing data interpretation and interfacing in energy systems analysis,” *Energy and AI*, vol. 5, p. 100074, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.egyai.2021.100074.
- [4] M. Curado Malta and A. A. Baptista, “A Method for the Development of Dublin Core Application Profiles (Me4DCAP V0.2): Detailed Description,”

Contact

Stephan Ferez

stephan.ferenz@uol.de

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